

**BEYOND THE PANDEMIC: ADDRESSING STABILITY AND ACCESS mRNA VACCINES -
A REVIEW**

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ABSTRACT

mRNA vaccines have emerged as a powerful alternative to traditional vaccines due to their high potency, safety, efficacy, and potential for rapid, cost-effective production and clinical development. Once considered a scientific curiosity, they have now become leading tools in combating the COVID-19 pandemic. The advancements in nanotechnology, particularly in developing delivery systems for mRNA vaccines, have played a crucial role in their success. This review provides a comprehensive overview of mRNA vaccines, discussing their structural components, mechanisms of immune activation, and the role of lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) in delivery. It also outlines the upstream, downstream, and formulation processes involved in mRNA vaccine manufacturing, along with an overview of current clinical trials.

KEYWORDS: mRNA vaccine immune response, mRNA vaccine clinical trials, lipid nanoparticles (LNPs), PEGylated lipids, lyophilized mRNA vaccines.

INTRODUCTION

Vaccination stands as one of humanity's greatest^[1] achievements in preventing the spread of infectious diseases. Beyond its vital role in protecting public health, vaccination significantly strengthens the economic sustainability of healthcare systems by reducing the costs associated^[2] with treating infectious illnesses. Moreover, vaccines play a crucial part in minimizing the risk and impact of disease outbreaks. The COVID-19 pandemic further highlighted the far-reaching benefits of vaccination not only in safeguarding individual health but also in supporting social and economic stability.

Through successful immunization programs, humanity has eradicated deadly diseases such as smallpox, nearly^[3] eliminated polio, and mounted a strong defence against COVID-19.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), vaccines prevent an estimated 2–3 million deaths each

year from diseases like pertussis, tetanus, influenza, and measles. Over time, vaccine development has evolved from the use of inactivated or attenuated pathogens to more advanced formulations such as subunit vaccines, which contain specific pathogen components to elicit immune responses. Major milestones in vaccine research include the advent of recombinant viral-vector vaccines, virus-like particle vaccines, conjugate polysaccharide or protein-based vaccines, and toxoid vaccines. Among these, the development of mRNA vaccines represents a transformative breakthrough—marked by their unprecedented speed of design, approval, and production during the COVID-19 pandemic, and their unique mechanism of inducing immune responses through intracellular antigen expression. We are now in the era of mRNA vaccines—an achievement built upon more than three decades of foundational research. Early studies in the 1990s demonstrated that *in vitro transcribed* (IVT) mRNA vaccines could effectively induce epitope presentation in animal models. However, their

therapeutic development was limited until the late 20th century, when critical technological breakthroughs validated the approach.

Over the past decade, significant^[4] innovations have enhanced the overall quality and functionality of mRNA vaccines, including

- i. Improved stability** through optimized capping, tailing, point mutations, and advanced purification methods.
- ii. Enhanced delivery** using lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) as efficient carriers.
- iii. Reduced immunogenicity** by incorporating modified nucleotides to minimize unwanted immune activation.

Compared to conventional vaccine platforms—such as live-attenuated, subunit-based, or DNA vaccines—mRNA vaccines offer several distinct advantages

- i. Safety:** mRNA is non-infectious and does not integrate into the host genome.
- ii. Efficacy:** Structural modifications improve stability and translation efficiency while lowering unintended immune responses.
- iii. Manufacturing efficiency:** mRNA vaccines can be produced rapidly and cost-effectively in a cell-free system, enabling large-scale production.

For instance, a 5-liter bioreactor can generate approximately one million doses of an mRNA vaccine in a single batch. Moreover, mRNA platforms^[5] allow for the encoding of multiple antigens within a single construct, offering the potential for stronger and broader immune protection against complex or resilient pathogens.

The true potential of mRNA vaccine technology was realized with the rapid development and approval of COVID-19 vaccines by Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna. These vaccines were created in an unprecedented timeframe—less than a year after the global outbreak of SARS-CoV-2, which caused widespread illness, hospitalizations, and deaths. The swift development of **Comirnaty** (Pfizer-BioNTech) and **Spikevax** (Moderna), followed by their large-scale administration to millions worldwide, played a pivotal role in controlling the pandemic.

The successful design, approval, and large-scale manufacturing of these vaccines firmly established the mRNA platform as a safe, effective, and adaptable tool for immunization.

This success has also sparked immense scientific interest in exploring mRNA technologies as a foundation for future prophylactic vaccines.

In this review, we present a comprehensive overview of mRNA vaccines, covering their structural components, pharmacological mechanisms, and the molecular

modifications that enhance their performance. We also explain how mRNA vaccines trigger immune responses within the host. Particular emphasis^[6] is placed on lipid-based delivery systems, especially **lipid nanoparticles (LNPs)**, which are crucial for efficient mRNA encapsulation and transport. Additionally, the review explores the structure and functional roles of LNPs, as well as recent advancements in (FIG1) **second-generation mRNA vaccines** and the ongoing **clinical trials** driving the next phase of vaccine innovation.

Fig. 1: mRNA Vaccine.

HISTORY

The journey of mRNA vaccines has unfolded over several decades, beginning with early experiments that explored how messenger RNA could be used to guide the immune system. One of the earliest milestones^[7] came in 2008, when an investigational mRNA-based therapy was tested for prostate cancer. The goal was to train the patient's immune cells to recognize and destroy cancerous tissue. The encouraging results from that study sparked wider interest in the therapeutic potential of mRNA technology.

By 2013, the first mRNA-related therapeutic, Provenge, gained approval for use in prostate cancer. Although not a traditional mRNA vaccine, it demonstrated how a patient's own immune cells could be engineered to target cancer, reinforcing confidence in the broader mRNA platform.

Around the same time, researchers began exploring mRNA vaccines for infectious diseases. A significant step forward occurred in 2013 when scientists at the University of Pennsylvania and the National Institutes of Health developed an experimental mRNA vaccine targeting the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) coronavirus. The vaccine performed successfully in animal studies, proving that mRNA could be used to generate protective immunity against viral infections.

The true turning point arrived in late 2019 with the global spread of COVID-19. Within a year, two mRNA vaccines — produced by Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna — received emergency use authorization in the United

States in December 2020. These vaccines demonstrated high levels of protection and rapidly became key tools in controlling the pandemic. Since then, millions of people worldwide have been vaccinated, firmly establishing mRNA technology as a transformative force in modern medicine.

The modern mRNA vaccines^[8] we know today are built on decades of scientific groundwork that began in the 1990s at the University of Wisconsin. That early research laid the foundation for the rapid development of the first COVID-19 mRNA vaccines, produced by Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna, which moved from concept to approval in an unprecedented timeframe.

The Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine emerged from the work of Dr. Ugur Şahin and Dr. Özlem Türeci, the physician-scientist duo who co-founded BioNTech in 2008 with the goal of advancing mRNA-based cancer immunotherapies. Their efforts to harness mRNA for directing the immune system against cancer revealed how effectively mRNA could instruct cells to generate specific proteins that trigger targeted immune responses. When SARS-CoV-2 appeared, this understanding allowed their team to swiftly adapt the technology to create a vaccine against the virus.

Moderna's vaccine followed a different scientific path. The company's early progress stemmed from research inspired by Dr. Derrick Rossi, whose work explored reprogramming adult cells to behave like embryonic stem cells using modified mRNA. This breakthrough helped establish Moderna's broader mRNA platform, enabling the company to rapidly design and produce its

COVID-19 vaccine candidate once the viral genetic sequence became available.

Together, these parallel scientific journeys—one rooted in cancer immunotherapy and the other in cellular reprogramming—converged to deliver the first widely used mRNA vaccines during the COVID-19.

Early research

Researchers at the University of Wisconsin first proposed^[9] the idea of using mRNA as a vaccine platform in the 1990s. Early work centred on using mRNA to activate the immune system against cancer cells. By the early 2000s, scientists had begun extending this concept to infectious diseases, investigating mRNA-based approaches for viruses like influenza and Zika.

A major step forward came in 2012, when scientists at Imperial College London developed a self-amplifying mRNA vaccine system. Soon after, in 2013, Moderna launched its first Phase 1 clinical trial testing a personalised cancer vaccine built on mRNA technology.

Development of mRNA vaccines

mRNA vaccines are created by packaging a small segment of genetic code from a virus into a protective shell made of lipid nanoparticles. These nanoparticles safeguard the fragile mRNA and help it enter human cells. Once inside, the mRNA (FIG2) provides instructions for cells to make a specific viral protein. The immune system recognises this protein as foreign and builds a defence against it, preparing the body to fight the actual virus if exposure occurs.

Fig. No. 2: Development of Mrna Vaccines.

➤ Advantages

❖ High Efficacy

mRNA vaccines have shown strong effectiveness in clinical studies. Both the Pfizer-BioNTech and Moderna COVID-19 vaccines achieved more than 90% protection in trials. Their high performance comes from their ability to activate both antibody-mediated immunity and T-cell responses.

❖ Rapid Development

A major strength of mRNA vaccines is how quickly they can be designed and manufactured. Because they rely on genetic sequences and can be produced using computer-guided design and synthesizers, new vaccines (FIG3) can be created in a matter of weeks. This speed is especially valuable during fast-spreading outbreaks.

❖ Safety Profile

mRNA vaccines do not use live or inactivated viruses, which reduces the risk associated with traditional vaccine platforms. They also generally don't require added

adjuvants, which may lower the likelihood of certain side effects. Overall, they provide a safer alternative while still generating a strong immune response.

Fig. No. 3: Development of Mrna In Dendritic Cell.

➤ Disadvantages

❖ Challenging Storage Conditions

A key limitation is the need for very^[9] low storage temperatures. Some mRNA vaccines must be kept at extremely cold conditions, such as -70°C , which complicates transport and storage. This requirement increases cost and limits access in regions without advanced cold-chain systems.

❖ Limited Early Supply

Manufacturing mRNA vaccines involves complex technology and specialized equipment. Scaling up production can take time, which may lead to shortages during urgent health situations like global pandemics.

❖ Uncertain Long-Term Data

As mRNA vaccines are relatively new, long-term safety information is still being gathered. However, current evidence from trials and real-world use indicates that they are safe, with most reported side effects being mild to moderate.

➤ The Pharmacology of mRNA Vaccines

▪ mRNA Structure

An mRNA molecule enables efficient translation of the DNA genetic sequence to the desired production of proteins by the ribosomes in the cytoplasm of the cells. Non-replicating mRNA and self-amplifying RNA are the two major types of mRNAs that are being investigated as candidate antigens for potential vaccines. The conventional, non-replicating mRNA-based vaccines encode the desired antigen for the immunogenic reaction containing the 5' and 3' untranslated regions (UTRs) and open reading frame (ORF), also called the coding region and the poly(A) tail. The self-amplifying mRNA contains all these components with an additional coding region in their ORF which codes for viral replication machinery which enables continuous intracellular RNA amplification followed by amplified antigen expression. In vitro transcription (IVT) is a reaction in which a linearized DNA plasmid containing the gene of interest is transcribed to the mRNA sequence.

▪ 5' Cap

The 5' end of the mRNA contains a 7-methylguanosine (m7G) moiety, followed by a triphosphate moiety to the first nucleotide (m7GpppN). m7GpppN is called a 5' cap which is a protective structure which protects RNA from exonuclease cleavage, regulates pre- mRNA splicing, and initiates mRNA translation and nuclear export of the mRNA to the cytoplasm. The 5' cap is also essential in recognition of non-self mRNA or exogenous mRNA from self mRNA or the endogenous mRNA by the innate immune system. The mRNA can be modified to improve its efficacy and stability by introducing many post-transcriptional modifications. Some of these include 2'-O-methylation at position 2' of the ribose ring at the first nucleotide (Cap 1, m7GpppN1m) and the second nucleotide e (Cap 2, m7GpppN1mN2m) as well. These modifications^[10] in the 5' cap structure not only increase the translation efficiency of mRNA but also stop activation of endosomal and cytosolic receptors, including RIG-I and MDA5, which act as defensive mechanisms against viral mRNA. Hence, the 2'-O-methylation of the 5' cap structure is a highly desirable property for increasing and enhancing the protein production from the mRNA after its transcription and to block any undesirable immune responses from the host immune system to the antigenic IVT mRNA.

▪ 5' and 3' UTRs

Although UTRs are not translated into the desired antigen or a protein, they are involved in regulating mRNA expression. These regions are located between the ORF and the 5' and 3' ends, in the upstream and the downstream of the mRNA. These UTRs contain regulatory sequences which are associated with the stability of mRNA and the efficient and correct translation of the mRNA. They also help in the recognition of mRNA by ribosomes and help in post-transcriptional modification of the mRNA. The mRNA translation and its half-life can be improved by the inclusion of cis-regulatory sequences in the UTRs.

Additionally, inclusion of naturally occurring sequences such as those derived from alpha- and beta-globin's have been widely used to design mRNA constructs for vaccines. Zeng *et al.* designed de novo 5' UTR sequences based on the guanine-cytosine (GC) content and its (GC) length for the development of mRNA vaccines.

▪ Poly(A) Tail

The IVT mRNA has a polyadenylated section at its 3' end which is known as the poly(A) tail. This polyadenylated tail is essential for determining the lifespan of the mRNA. The poly(A) tails of the naturally occurring mRNA molecules in mammalian cells have a longer length of approximately 250 nucleotides (nt), which gets gradually shortened throughout the lifespan of mRNA in the cytosol. Since the tail size affects the degradation of mRNA, the incorporation of poly(A) tails is desirable in the production of mRNA vaccines and therapeutics with longer half-life. The addition of

approximately 100 nt to the poly(A) tail can result in the production of mRNA with desired prolongation of degradation.

Modified Nucleotides

Natural mRNA and other RNA molecules^[11] contain ATP, CTP, GTP, and UTP as the four basic nucleotides. After the post-transcriptional modification of the mRNA molecules, some of the nucleotides get modified, such as pseudo uridine and 5-methylcytidine. These modified nucleotides can be utilized in the IVT transcription of the mRNA. Although non- modified mRNA has its own advantage, modified nucleotides are beneficial in the sense that they can avoid the recognition of IVT mRNA by the innate immune system, thus avoiding any undesirable immune responses, and improving the translation efficiency of the mRNA to the desired antigen. Andries *et al.* demonstrated that mRNAs containing the N (1)-methyl- pseudo uridine (m1Ψ) modification outperformed the pseudo uridine (Ψ)-modified mRNA platform by providing up to approximately 44-fold higher and 13-fold higher reporter gene expression upon transfection into cell lines or mice, respectively. The authors also demonstrated that (m5C/) m1Ψ-modified mRNA resulted in a reduction in intracellular innate immunogenicity upon in vitro transfection. The modification results in controlled activation of the toll-like receptor 3 (TLR3) and initiates the downstream innate immune signaling, which is a desired characteristic of an mRNA vaccine.

Innate and Adaptive Immune Stimulation by mRNA Vaccines

A vaccine consisting of a pathogen-specific immunogen (encoding the viral protein) and an adjuvant can help in stimulating adaptive immune responses. While the adjuvant is designed to stimulate the innate immune response and provide the signal for T cell activation, an optimal adjuvant should stimulate^[12] innate immune response without inducing any systemic inflammation, which can elicit severe side effects. For mRNA vaccines, the mRNA molecule serves as both immunogen and adjuvant, due to the intrinsic immunostimulatory properties of mRNA. mRNA vaccination, once administered intramuscularly, leads to potential adaptive

Immune system activation by the following pathways

- (i) Transfection of muscle cells and epidermal cells.
- (ii) Transfection of tissue-resident immune cells such as the dendritic cells (DC), macrophages, and Langerhans cells at the site of injection, thereby initiating the priming of T and B cells, and (iii) transport of secondary lymphoid tissues, such as the lymph nodes (LNs) and the spleen. The host cell recognizes single-stranded RNA (ssRNA) and double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) by various endosomal and cytosolic innate receptors that form a critical part of the human innate immune response to exogenous viruses. Toll-like receptors (TLR3 and TLR7) bind to the exogenous ssRNA in the

endosome, and inflammation signaling receptors including RIG-I, MDA5, NOD2, and PKR bind to ssRNA and dsRNA in the cytosol. This results in cellular activation, and generation^[13] of type I interferon and other multiple inflammatory mediators. Type I interferon has an inhibitory action on cellular translation, which can suppress the amount of the antigen produced by the mRNA vaccines. The currently available mRNA vaccines contain purified IVT mRNA which is single-stranded in nature and contains modified nucleotides. This helps in reducing the binding to TLR3 and TLR7, and immune sensors, therefore limiting excessive production of type I interferon and its inhibitory effect on cellular translation of the mRNA. mRNA vaccines transfect tissue-resident immune cells, including APCs, such as DCs and macrophages.

➤ PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

The pathophysiology of mRNA vaccines involves the delivery of synthetic mRNA, which is then translated by the host's ribosomes into a specific viral or bacterial protein, such as a spike protein. This protein is presented to the immune system by antigen-presenting cells (APCs), triggering an adaptive immune response without the risks of a live or inactivated pathogen. The process does not integrate into the host's genome and the mRNA is eventually degraded by the body.

➤ How mRNA vaccines work

- **Delivery:** The synthetic mRNA is enclosed in a protective lipid nanoparticle to help it enter cells.
- **Cellular entry:** The lipid nanoparticle^[14] is taken up by antigen-presenting cells (APCs) through endocytosis.
- **Translation:** The mRNA escapes the endosome and enters the cytosol, where it is translated by the cell's ribosomes into a specific viral or bacterial protein.
- **Immune response:** The APCs present this foreign protein to other immune cells, triggering an adaptive immune response that includes the production of antibodies and memory cells.
- **Degradation:** The body naturally breaks down the mRNA, so it does not remain in the cell indefinitely.

➤ PHASES OF mRNA vaccine

The "phases" of mRNA vaccines can refer to two distinct processes: the stages of **development and approval**, and the steps of how the vaccine **works in the body** (mechanism of action).

❖ Phases of mRNA Vaccine Development and Approval

The development and approval process for mRNA vaccines, while capable of acceleration during a pandemic, generally follows^[15] the standard phases for any new vaccine:

1. **Exploratory/Research Phase:** This initial stage involves identifying potential antigens (e.g., the virus's spike protein sequence) and developing the

fundamental technology, including optimizing the mRNA sequence and the delivery system, such as lipid nanoparticles (LNPs).

2. **Preclinical Phase:** Researchers conduct laboratory and animal studies to assess the vaccine candidate's safety and its ability to elicit an immune response (immunogenicity).
3. **Clinical Development (Human Trials):** If preclinical results are promising, an Investigational New Drug (IND) application is filed with regulatory agencies (like the FDA), allowing for human trials, which are typically divided into three phases:

Phase 1: The vaccine is given to a small group (20-100) of healthy volunteers to evaluate its safety, identify potential side effects, and determine if it provokes an immune response.

Phase 2: The study expands to several^[16] hundred participants to gather more safety data, determine the optimal dosage and schedule, and further assess immunogenicity.

Phase 3: This large-scale, randomized, placebo-controlled trial involves thousands of participants to confirm the vaccine's efficacy in preventing the disease and to monitor for less common side effects.

4. **Regulatory Review and Approval:** Data from all phases are submitted to national regulatory authorities (e.g., FDA in the U.S.) for a thorough review. If the vaccine is deemed safe and effective, it is approved for general use.
5. **Manufacturing and Quality Control:** Large-scale production begins, with continuous quality control and adherence to regulatory requirements (Good Manufacturing Practices, or cGMP).
6. **Post-Marketing Surveillance (Phase 4):** Ongoing, formal studies are conducted after approval to monitor the vaccine's long-term safety and effectiveness in the general population.

➤ ETIOLOGY

The term "etiology" is not applicable^[17] to mRNA vaccines, as etiology refers to the cause of a disease. Instead, the user is likely asking about the **development** or **mechanism of action** of mRNA vaccines. mRNA vaccines were developed using the genetic sequence of a pathogen, like the SARS-CoV-2 virus, to instruct cells to produce a specific protein (such as a spike protein) from that pathogen. This process triggers an immune response that builds immunity without causing disease.

- **Genetic sequence:** Scientists use the genetic blueprint (mRNA) of a virus, like the one that causes COVID-19, to create the vaccine.
- **Cellular instruction:** Once injected, the mRNA instructions are taken up by the body's cells.
- **Protein production:** The cells use the instructions to produce a specific protein from the virus, such as the spike protein on the surface of SARS-CoV-2.
- **Immune response:** The body recognizes^[18] this protein as foreign and mounts an immune response to it, creating antibodies and immune cells that will fight the real virus if encountered in the future.

- **Safe and effective:** The mRNA is quickly broken down by the body and does not enter the cell's nucleus or alter the person's DNA.

➤ RISK FACTORS

The primary risk factor associated with mRNA vaccines is the risk of myocarditis and pericarditis, especially in young males after the second dose. Other concerns include the potential for rare, more severe adverse events like those that can occur with any vaccine, though scientific reviews largely support the high safety levels of mRNA platforms and note the absence of genomic integration risk.

❖ Myocarditis and pericarditis

- **Risk:** Inflammation of the heart muscle (myocarditis) or the outer lining of the heart (pericarditis) has been associated with mRNA COVID-19 vaccines.
- **Higher risk group:** The risk is highest in young men between 12 and 24 years old.
- **Severity:** While often mild and manageable, more severe^[19] cases, including fulminant myocarditis leading to death, have been reported.
- **Outcomes:** Some patients with vaccine-induced myocarditis may show signs of heart injury on an MRI (late gadolinium enhancement), and some may experience persistent symptoms requiring medication or activity restrictions for months.

Other potential risk factors

- **Allergic reactions:** As with any vaccine, allergic reactions are a possibility.
- **Genomic integration:** While a theoretical concern, scientific reviews generally conclude^[20] there is no risk of the mRNA vaccine's genetic material integrating into the recipient's DNA.

➤ EPIDIMIOLOGY

The epidemiology of mRNA vaccines focuses^[21] on their impact on disease spread and severity, such as reducing COVID-19-related emergency department visits and hospitalizations, as seen in young children where vaccination with two or more doses was 40% effective in preventing these outcomes. Epidemiological studies also evaluate the effectiveness of newer vaccine variants, such as those adapted for the JN.1 variant, against circulating strains.

- **Preventing severe illness:** mRNA vaccines have been shown to reduce the risk of severe outcomes from infections like COVID-19. In young children aged 6 months to 4 years, receiving two or more doses of the COVID-19 mRNA vaccine was associated with a 40% effectiveness in preventing emergency department (ED) visits and hospitalizations.
- **Vaccine effectiveness against new variants:** Epidemiology is used to determine^[22] the effectiveness of updated mRNA vaccines. For example, studies are evaluating the protective effects

of newer mRNA vaccines (like those adapted for the JN.1 variant) against specific variants that cause hospitalization and death.

- **Surveillance and data collection:** Epidemiological studies use surveillance networks and designs like the test-negative case-control study to collect data on vaccine effectiveness and the broader epidemiology of the disease in vaccinated and unvaccinated populations.
- **Safety and effectiveness over time:** Epidemiological research continues to monitor the safety and effectiveness of mRNA vaccines as new variants emerge and as more time passes since initial vaccination campaigns.

➤ Mortality

Studies have shown that mRNA vaccines do not increase the overall risk of death. In fact, vaccinated individuals have been found to have a lower rate of all-cause mortality compared to unvaccinated individuals, which is partly attributed^[1] to the protective effects of the vaccine against COVID-19. Reports of death following vaccination^[23] have been thoroughly reviewed, and causal links are only established in extremely rare cases, often involving individuals with severe pre-existing health conditions where a definitive link could not be entirely ruled out.

➤ Complications

Most reported adverse events are common, mild-to-moderate, and transient, usually resolving within a few days of vaccination.

These include

- Pain at the injection site
- Fatigue
- Headache
- Muscle pain and chills
- Fever

➤ CLINICAL TRIALS

Clinical trials for mRNA vaccines are underway for a variety of diseases beyond COVID-19, including infectious^[24] diseases and cancer. These trials are testing the efficacy and safety of mRNA technology in different contexts, such as using personalized cancer vaccines or combining mRNA vaccines with other treatments like immunotherapy. Research is also focused on improving the technology itself, for example, by enhancing the stability, delivery, and immune response of the mRNA vaccines.

❖ Current status and applications

- **Infectious diseases:** While the initial success of mRNA vaccines was with COVID-19, further clinical trials are ongoing for other infectious diseases, with an RSV vaccine already approved based on successful Phase 3 trials.
- **Cancer:**
 - **Personalized vaccines:** Trials are testing

personalized mRNA vaccines that target specific mutations in a patient's tumour, often with the aim of treating existing cancers like melanoma.

- **Combination therapy:** Preliminary results have prompted a large Phase III trial for a randomized^[25] study to determine if mRNA COVID-19 vaccines given to cancer patients can improve their response to immunotherapy.
- **Ongoing research:** Scientists continue to work on improving mRNA vaccine platforms. Challenges being addressed include the need for modifications to improve translation efficiency, the development of effective delivery systems like lipid nanoparticles, and the reduction of unwanted innate immune responses.

➤ CONCLUSION

Years of progress in messenger RNA (mRNA) engineering and delivery systems have transformed mRNA vaccines into a powerful strategy for preventing infectious diseases and responding rapidly to global health emergencies. The rapid development of the first mRNA vaccines against SARS-CoV-2 demonstrated the remarkable flexibility and speed of this platform. These vaccines not only performed beyond initial expectations but also established a solid scientific and technological base for future advancements in mRNA-based immunization. Ongoing clinical trials suggest that mRNA vaccines may soon compete with, or even replace, traditional vaccine approaches. In addition to infectious diseases, mRNA technology also holds promise for designing more effective vaccines against persistent pathogens and for developing novel cancer therapies.

Although early preclinical studies generated considerable enthusiasm regarding the benefits of mRNA vaccines, recent clinical findings have introduced a more balanced perspective. In some human trials, immune responses were less robust than those predicted from animal studies, similar to observations made with DNA vaccine platforms. Moreover, certain adverse effects were reported and cannot be overlooked. It is important to note that these outcomes reflect only specific versions of mRNA vaccine designs, and variations in formulation, expression efficiency, and immune stimulation may produce different results. Continued research is essential to better understand species-specific immune responses to mRNA components, optimize immune signalling pathways in humans, and refine vaccine design for improved safety and efficacy.

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